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THE IMPLICATIONS OF SHUTTER CONTROL: A BASIS FOR INVOKING FORCE MAJEURE IN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA LICENSES

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ABSTRACT

The commercialization of Earth observation technology has created a tension between national security interests and contractual obligations in satellite data licensing. The paper examines whether shutter control policies can justify invoking force majeure clauses in satellite data license agreements. Earth observation has become commercially vital for both the public and private sectors. However, the commercialization of the activity raises national security concerns and has led countries, such as the United States of America (US), to adopt a ‘shutter control’ policy. The policy allows countries to compel satellite operators to cease data collection, potentially preventing licensors from fulfilling contractual obligations. The paper specifically focuses on the US shutter control policy, which originates from the Presidential Decision Directive 23. The policy permits the government to limit data collection to safeguard national security interests, although its ambiguity may lead to disputes in commercial agreements and invoke the force majeure clause. The paper compares the application of force majeure under UK common law, which applies the restrictive doctrine of frustration, and Indonesian civil law, which recognizes broader concepts of force majeure. The review finds that the enforceability of the force majeure clause is strongly influenced by the choice of governing law and the application of the shutter control policy. The analysis concludes that while invoking the force majeure clause may be justified by the implementation of the shutter control policy, its enforceability is conditioned on both the suitability of the governing legal framework and the precision of the contractual terms.

KEYWORDS: Shutter control, Earth observation, Data licensing, Force Majeure, Commercialization.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Earth observation, also known as remote sensing, provides diverse benefits for global economic development. It plays a pivotal role in, among other things, monitoring environmental changes, managing natural resources, and responding to disasters.² Today's technology makes Earth observation commercially feasible. The consequence of this significant development is that Earth observation has become an indispensable tool for both public and private sectors.

At the same time, the meaningful benefits and the rapid expansion of Earth observation into a commercial activity have not been without complications. Data-related issues remain the primary legal challenge in commercializing earth observation activity.³ The reason behind such issues is the concern of national security, which may be jeopardized due to private operations that collect remote sensing data.⁴ One safeguard taken by countries to maintain their national security interests is the so-called 'shutter control', as the United States of America (US) and Canada practice through their remote sensing regulation.⁵ The shutter control is generally understood as a measure that allows a State to block the satellite operator from taking images of the Earth by closing the 'shutter' of the camera or other remote sensing equipment.⁶

The application of shutter control measures may pose a contractual issue for the commercial activity of remote sensing, which is generally governed by a data license agreement. The enactment of the shutter control policy could prevent satellite operators or data processors from fulfilling their contractual obligations, either by restricting data acquisition over specific locations or by withholding data from the end users. As the shutter control policy compels the satellite operator to switch off the remote sensing equipment in the satellite, the satellite operator or the data processor could argue that it is a force majeure and they do not need to bear any responsibility or liability for any damages incurred by the end user for complying with the policy.

Similar to other commercial contracts, the data license agreement commonly includes a force majeure clause that excuses the parties from performing their contractual obligations in the event of unforeseeable or unavoidable events beyond both parties' control. Inclusion of such a clause is a common standard practice in commercial contract drafting. In the present scenario, the force majeure clause could serve as a legal basis for the satellite operator or data processor to limit their exposure or to defend against any claims arising from compliance with the policy.

The legal reasoning of the above argument may hold if all the parties involved are companies subject to US law, i.e., established under US law. However, as the world enters a period of globalization, such a situation could occur in a cross-border transaction involving multiple jurisdictions. For example, a transaction that involves a US satellite operator, a UK data seller, and an Indonesian consumer. The cross-border commercial transaction nature, involving multiple legal systems, presents a legal issue in implementing the data license agreement in the event of the enactment of the shutter control policy. It raises the question, can shutter control serve as a legal basis for invoking the force majeure clause under a data license agreement in cross-border commercial contexts?

² Couture, J., & Golovtchenko, V. (2025, January 17). Earth Observation: 5 Uses of Data for Business and the Planet. World Economic Forum; World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2025/01/5-uses-earth-observation-satellite-data-for-business-and-planet/>.

³ Masson-Zwaan, T., & Hofmann, M. (2025). *An Introduction to Space Law* (5th ed.). Wolters Kluwer, 208.

⁴ *Ibid*, 209.

⁵ *Ibid*.

⁶ *Ibid*.

To address the questions, the paper will first discuss the commercial relations in Earth observation activities in Section 2. In Section 3, the paper will discuss the shutter control policy, particularly under the US regulations. The paper will then discuss and compare the force majeure situation under the United Kingdom (UK) Law (common law system) and Indonesian Law (civil law system) in section 4. Section 5 of the paper will analyze the application of force majeure arising from the US's shutter control. The paper will conclude its discussion in the final section.

The paper will refer to the UK Common Law system as it is widely regarded as one of the most well-established legal frameworks, particularly in the domain of contract law. Its strength lies in several key features: (i) an independent judiciary and strong adherence to the rule of law, which foster trust and confidence in commercial dealings; (ii) a legal framework that is clear, fair, and predictable, supported by a robust system of precedent; and (iii) the international recognition and enforceability of UK court decisions, which enhance legal certainty across jurisdictions.⁷

Meanwhile, the Indonesian legal system continues to rely on the old Dutch Civil Code, a legacy of its colonial past. It adopted the Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*) and was promulgated in 1847.⁸ Since then, Indonesia has used the code to govern the civil relations of its people. The country is yet to reform or update its civil code, despite it having been in use for nearly two centuries. A fitness check is necessary to see whether such an ancient civil code is equipped to address a developing, highly advanced, and complex space industry.⁹

The paper will review the law's applicability to addressing contemporary challenges in the space industry, specifically in the context of the enactment of shutter control policies. This inclusion offers a comparative perspective on how these two legal traditions address potential concerns in space activities.

2. THE COMMERCIAL RELATIONSHIP IN EARTH OBSERVATION ACTIVITIES

Satellite data is the central component in the commercialization of Earth observation or remote-sensing activities.¹⁰ However, satellite data will become commercially valuable and be sold only after analysis and processing.¹¹ The satellite data must undergo analysis and processing to be converted into identifiable data and meet its intended purpose.¹² The satellite data will not have significant commercial value without analysis and processing, as its value lies in the high-resolution images captured by satellites.¹³

As the commercial value of satellite data depends on the data supplier's processing and analysis capabilities, the data supplier consequently retains control over how the Earth observation data is accessed and distributed to the relevant market. The situation prompts users to obtain access to the data from the relevant data controller through a commercial transaction, marking the beginning of the

⁷ Courts and Tribunals Judiciary. (2017). The strength of English law and the UK jurisdiction. In Courts and Tribunals Judiciary. <https://www.judiciary.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/legaluk-strength-of-english-law-draft-4-FINAL.pdf>.

⁸ Hutabarat, S. (2016). Harmonisasi Hukum Kontrak dan Dampaknya Pada Hukum Kontrak Indonesia. *Veritas et Justitia*, 2(1), 112–134, 118.

⁹ Khuan, H. (2025). The Urgency of Civil Law Reform in Responding to the Development of Artificial Intelligence in Automatic Contracts. *Journal Hukum Dan Keadilan*, 2(4), 1–9, 2–3. <https://doi.org/10.61942/jhk.v2i4.363>.

¹⁰ Hayward, C. M. (1990). Remote Sensing: Terrestrial Laws for Celestial Activities Note. *Boston University International Law Journal*, 8(1), 157–186, 168.

¹¹ Kim, Y.-J. (2024). Commercial Use of Satellite Remote Sensing Data and Civil Liability. *Laws*, 13(6), 77–98, 80. <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws13060077>.

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Tronchetti, F. (2015). Legal aspects of satellite remote sensing. In F. G. von der Dunk (Ed.), *Handbook of space law: Research Handbooks in International Law series*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 509–510.

data-commercialization process.¹⁴ The transaction is commonly governed through an agreement known as the ‘satellite data license agreement’.¹⁵ Through this agreement, the data suppliers maintain control over the dissemination of satellite data and generate revenue. Data suppliers or the licensor will impose obligations on users or licensees to pay a license fee and to impose limitations on data use, such as prohibiting the resale or sublicensing of satellite data to third parties.¹⁶

Although the sale transaction appears straightforward, the legal relationship that needs to be formed to enable such a transaction may be more complex. Indeed, the transaction typically involves only the suppliers and the users. However, in some instances, the data suppliers may not be the owners or operators of Earth observation satellites.¹⁷ Consequently, according to Young-Ju Kim, the legal relationship in Earth observation commercialization can be classified into three types.¹⁸

The first type is the common relation, which only involves the licensor and licensee. In this case, the licensor operates its satellite and sensor, analyzes and processes the satellite data, and sells it directly to the users.¹⁹ Thus, the satellite data license agreement governs the legal relationship between the licensor and the licensee.

Figure 1. Type 1 relationship.

Unlike a type 1 relationship, a type 2 relationship involves a separation of roles. In this arrangement, the company that operates the satellite and the sensing sensor does not handle the data analysis and processing.²⁰ The satellite data is analyzed and processed by a different company (third party), which subsequently becomes the seller of such data to the consumer.²¹ The relationship between the operator and the third party is governed by a contract for analyzing, processing, and selling the data, while the license agreement governs the relationship between the third party and the end-user.²²

¹⁴ Kim, *supra* note 11 at 81.

¹⁵ Tronchetti, *supra* note 13 at 549; Mantl, L. (2023). Law and Policy of Data from Space: Satellite Navigation and Remote Sensing. In P. J. Blount & M. Hofmann (Eds.), *Space law in a networked world*. Brill Nijhoff, 203–204.

¹⁶ Tronchetti, *supra* note 13 at 549.

¹⁷ Kim, *supra* note 11 at 81.

¹⁸ *Ibid*, 81–84.

¹⁹ *Ibid*, 81–82.

²⁰ *Ibid*, 82.

²¹ *Ibid*.

²² *Ibid*.

Figure 2. Type 2 relationship.

Type 3 also has a tripartite relationship with different arrangements from type 2. In the type 3 relationship, the satellite operator and the sensor operator are performed by two different companies.²³ The sensor operator will operate the sensor, analyze, process, and subsequently sell the satellite data to the end user under this structure.²⁴ The sensor operator company formalized its legal relationship with the satellite operator through the ‘Sensor Installation and Usage Agreement’.²⁵

Figure 3. Type 3 relationship.

²³ Ibid.

²⁴ Ibid.

²⁵ Ibid.

The abovementioned discussion shows that the commercialization of Earth observation activities may have an intricate legal framework, particularly when it involves a tripartite arrangement. The tripartite structure involves multiple contracts that assign distinct rights and obligations to the parties in a remote sensing operation. Understanding these relationships is essential for assessing whether the force majeure clause in a satellite data license agreement applies when a country enacts a shutter control policy. The interconnected nature of the tripartite structure may lead to disputes over liability, particularly between the licensor and its third-party partner, when a country exercises its shutter control policy.

3. THE US 'SHUTTER CONTROL' POLICY

Earth observation technology has advanced rapidly and has outpaced the applicable international legal framework, raising concerns about a country's practice of remotely sensing foreign countries and disseminating the resulting data commercially.²⁶ Given this development, countries establish national regulations on remote sensing to limit commercial sensing activities, especially on the collection or dissemination of sensing data.²⁷ The commercial limitation aims to protect national security interests and ensure exclusive access to the government in the event of national disasters or other national crises.²⁸ There are two methods available to countries for limiting remote sensing activities to preserve national security interests. The first one is the shutter control method, in which the country prevents data collection when there are concerns of national security, international obligations, or foreign policy interests.²⁹ The US and Canada are known to use the shutter control method in their national remote sensing regulations.³⁰ The second method is a distribution control method, in which the country reviews the remote sensing images before they are distributed to ensure that national security or other sensitive national information remains protected. Germany, France, Finland, and Japan are some countries that practice this method to preserve their security and other national interests.³¹ However, for the purposes of the paper, this section will focus solely on the shutter control policy adopted by the US.

It all began with the US's interest in commercializing its Landsat program in the 1970s. In 1972, the US established the Landsat program under the auspices of NASA.³² At the end of the 1970s, the US attempted to privatize the Landsat system through the 1984 *Land Remote Sensing Commercialization Act*.³³ The plan was to delegate the operation of the Landsat system to the private sector to make the system commercially viable and, eventually, to create a private-sector-driven ecosystem.³⁴ Unfortunately, the initiative did not unfold as intended due to rising data prices and competition from the *Satellite Pour l'Observation de la Terre* (SPOT) program, an earth observation satellite program funded by the French Government.³⁵ Subsequently, the US reinstated the Landsat program under the overall government oversight.³⁶ In 1992, the US enacted the *Land Remote Sensing Policy Act*, which placed the Landsat program under the

²⁶ Curran, P. J. (1985). Principles of remote sensing. Longman Publishing Group, 5–6; Hayward, *supra note* 10 at 158.

²⁷ Tronchetti, *supra note* 13 at 526.

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ Masson-Zwaan & Hofmann, *supra note* 3 at 209.

³⁰ For the application of shutter control in the US, *see* 15 CFR Part 960 on Licensing of Private Remote Sensing Space Systems; For the application of shutter control in Canada, *see* the Remote Sensing Space Systems Act 2005 section Interruptions of Service.

³¹ Kim, *supra note* 11 at 85 – 91; Masson-Zwaan & Hofmann, *supra note* 3 at 209.

³² Ito, A. (2011). Legal aspects of satellite remote sensing. Martinus Nijhoff, 75.

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ *Ibid.*; Tronchetti, *supra note* 13 at 528.

³⁵ Ito, *supra note* 32 at 76.

³⁶ *Ibid.*

auspices of the Department of Defense and NASA, while giving the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) the authority to issue licenses.³⁷

Over the years, US laws on remote sensing have continuously evolved in response to technological developments and contemporary commercial and social needs.³⁸ The *Land Remote Sensing Policy Act* maintains its status as the primary legal instrument governing remote sensing activities in the US.³⁹ However, other instruments have continuously updated and complemented the act, including the *Presidential Decision Directive 23* (PDD-23).⁴⁰ One of the PDD-23 objectives is to “specify national security measures as a licensing requirement”.⁴¹ In pursuit of this objective, PDD-23 incorporates a shutter-control provision empowering the executive branch of the US government to:⁴²

[...] may, after consultation with the appropriate agency(ies), require the licensee to limit data collection and/or distribution by the system to the extent necessitated by the given situation [...].⁴³

The provision aims to avoid compromising the US national security, international obligations, or foreign policy due to US commercial satellite activities.⁴⁴

The PDD-23 was eventually superseded by the *US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy*, which aims to enhance US remote sensing capabilities and the remote sensing industry.⁴⁵ The policy further deregulates restrictions provided under the PDD-23.⁴⁶ It states that the objective of the policy is to:

[...] advance and protect U.S. national security and foreign policy interest by maintaining the nation’s leadership in remote sensing space activities, and by sustaining and enhancing the U.S. remote sensing industry.⁴⁷

Despite the adoption of a new remote sensing policy, neither the PDD-23 nor the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy defines what constitutes a national security interest. It remains to give the executive branch of the US government the power to impose the policy over an undefined territorial scope for an undefined amount of time.⁴⁸ The broad terminology used in the PDD-23 subsequently drew criticism from many stakeholders.⁴⁹

In 2006, the US government adopted the regulation on Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems to enhance the implementation of the 1992 *Land Remote Sensing Policy Act*,⁵⁰ which provides

³⁷ Tronchetti, *supra* note 13 at 528.

³⁸ *Ibid*, 527.

³⁹ *Ibid*, 529; Ito, *supra* note 32 at 77.

⁴⁰ *Ibid*.

⁴¹ Ito, *supra* note 32 at 78.

⁴² Prober, R. (2003). Shutter Control: Confronting Tomorrow’s Technology with Yesterday’s Regulations Note. *Journal of Law & Politics*, 19(2), 203–252, 209.

⁴³ Presidential Decision Directive/NSC-23. (1994, March 9). Federation American Scientist. <https://irp.fas.org/offdocs/pdd/pdd-23.pdf>.

⁴⁴ *Ibid*.

⁴⁵ Ito, *supra* note 32, at 79 – 80.

⁴⁶ *Ibid*.

⁴⁷ *U.S. Commercial Remote Sensing Policy*, 25 April 2003. <https://www.nesdis.noaa.gov/s3/2021-08/Commercial%20Remote%20Sensing%20Policy%202003.pdf>.

⁴⁸ Prober, *supra* note 42 at 209.

⁴⁹ *Ibid*.

⁵⁰ See 15 C.F.R. Part 960 – Licensing of Private Remote Sensing Systems.

detailed procedures regarding licensing requirements, procedures, and compliance.⁵¹ Following this, the US government further removed certain restrictions by updating the *Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems Regulation* in 2020 to increase US competitiveness against foreign remote sensing operators.⁵² The latest version of the regulation divides remote sensing satellites into three categories based on their capability.⁵³

- a) Tier 1 satellites are those that have the capability to produce unenhanced data equivalent in quality to non-US remote sensing satellites and are subject to the least stringent licensing requirements, as they are assessed as low risk.
- b) Tier 2 satellites are those that have the capability to produce unenhanced data with the same quality as other US-licensed remote sensing satellites and are subject to more licensing requirements as they are deemed to have a higher risk than Tier 1.
- c) Tier 3 satellites are those that have the capability to produce unenhanced data that is unique or exceeds the capabilities of non-US and US-licensed remote sensing satellites, and consequently are subject to more extensive licensing requirements.

The updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems Regulation still incorporates the shutter control provision. However, it only applies to remote sensing satellites in the Tier 2 and Tier 3 categories.⁵⁴ Tier 1 remote sensing satellites are only obligated to operate in a manner that preserves US national security and to observe international obligations and policies.⁵⁵

Despite efforts to ease restrictions on commercial remote sensing operations, the updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems Regulation still reflects the shortcomings of PDD-23 and the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy. It still offers no definition of the concept of national security interest and foreign policy interest when applying the shutter control policy. It also continues to vest the executive branch of the US government with the authority to impose a shutter control policy over an undefined territorial scope. The updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation does, however, introduce a time limit on the application of the shutter control policy for Tier 3 categories. The updated version of the regulation caps them for three years unless requested otherwise by the Secretary of Defense or Secretary of State. No similar limitation is imposed on the Tier 2 category, leaving the duration of such conditions unresolved.

The above exploration of the US shutter control policy shows that maintaining the integrity of national security interests, upholding foreign policy, and fulfilling international obligations are the policy's main objectives. Nevertheless, some concepts remain undefined despite efforts to streamline the regulation. Furthermore, the temporal limit introduced in the recent version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation may still be extended upon request from the Secretary of Defense or the Secretary of State, which may result in uncertainty. These remaining legal gaps could open the door to a dispute between the commercial parties and indicate a justification for imposing the force majeure clause.

⁵¹ Ito, *supra note* 32 at 80.

⁵² Slivker, A. (2023, September). Global Outer Space Guide: United States. Norton Rose Fulbright; Norton Rose Fulbright.

<https://www.nortonrosefulbright.com/en-nl/knowledge/publications/08a2c80a/global-outer-space-guide-us>.

⁵³ See 15 C.F.R. § 960.6 – Application categorization.

⁵⁴ For remote sensing satellites under the Tier 2 category, see 15 C.F.R. § 960.9(a); For remote sensing satellites under the Tier 3 category, see 15 C.F.R. § 960.10(a).

⁵⁵ See 15 C.F.R. § 960.8(b).

4. FORCE MAJEURE COMPARISON BETWEEN COMMON LAW AND CIVIL LAW

4.1. *The United Kingdom Common Law*

Force majeure clauses are commonly found in commercial contracts. The clause usually appears in boilerplate form, which aims to excuse either party to a contract from performing their obligations due to events or circumstances beyond their control.⁵⁶ However, UK law does not recognize the concept of force majeure,⁵⁷ which is rooted in French civil law.⁵⁸ The UK law has a doctrine to discharge a contract due to supervening events, called the doctrine of frustration.⁵⁹ The UK courts rarely apply the doctrine of frustration, as discharge requires the highest degree of seriousness.⁶⁰ The UK law sets a high bar threshold since it highly upholds the principle of sanctity of contract (*pacta sunt servanda*).⁶¹ The UK courts have consistently upheld this position over the years.⁶² Therefore, the UK courts could still impose liability on a party under a contract despite the requirement to perform an impossible obligation.

Furthermore, UK law recognizes the doctrine of absolute contract, as established in *Paradine v. Jane*.⁶³ The court stipulated that when an obligation imposed by law cannot be fulfilled without fault, the obligation may be exempted.⁶⁴ Meanwhile, when an obligation arises from a contract, it must be fulfilled despite unforeseeable events.⁶⁵ Over time, the UK Courts began to recognize exceptions to this absolute approach, and later cases adopted a more flexible understanding of contractual obligations.

The case of *Taylor v. Caldwell* is known as a landmark case for adopting a more flexible approach, as it departed from the doctrine of absolute contract by establishing the doctrine of discharge.⁶⁶ The UK Courts found that a contract may be discharged if its performance depends on the continued existence of a specific object and the destruction of that object is not due to fault.⁶⁷ In other words, a contract may be discharged if performance becomes impossible (performance risk).⁶⁸ Other than the discharge doctrine, the prohibition of trading with an enemy, changing government policy, and prohibition by a foreign country may frustrate a contract.⁶⁹

⁵⁶ Jardine-Brown, R. (2016, January 6). Force majeure clauses under English law | Article | Chambers and Partners. Chambers and Partners; Chambers and Partners. <https://chambers.com/articles/force-majeure-clauses-under-english-law>; Thomson Reuters. (2024). Practical Law UK Signon. Thomson Reuters; Thomson Reuters. [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/3-107-5776?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)&firstPage=true](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/3-107-5776?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)&firstPage=true).

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ *Ralli Brothers v Compañía Naviera Sota Y Aznar*, (1920). <https://www.acerislaw.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/Ralli-Bros-v-Compania-Naviera-Sota-y-Aznar-1920-2-KB-287.pdf>, 292, 297, 301.

⁵⁹ Peel, E. (2022). Frustration and Force Majeure (4th ed.). Sweet & Maxwell, 59–63, 447–449.

⁶⁰ Ibid, 62–63.

⁶¹ Ibid, 1–4.

⁶² *Eurico SpA v Philipp Bros (The Epaphus)*, EWCA Civ J0515-5 (1987). <https://vlex.co.uk/vid/eurico-s-p-v-793161761>; *Jones and Another v The President and Scholars of St. John's College*, Oxford (1870).

⁶³ *Paradine and Jane Aleyn*, Hil. 22 Car. Rot. 1178 & 1179 (1647).

⁶⁴ Ibid.

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ *Taylor and Another against Caldwell and Another*, S. C. 32 L. J. Q. B. 164; 8 L. T. 356; 11 W. R. 726 (1863).

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ Peel, *supra note* 59 at 40–41.

⁶⁹ Ibid, 326–328; 342–344; 364–367.

4.2. Indonesian Civil Law

On the other hand, Indonesian civil law recognizes the concept of force majeure or *overmacht*. The provisions related to force majeure or *overmacht* can be found across the old Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*), which still serves as the Indonesian Civil Code to this date.⁷⁰ The Indonesian Civil Code stipulates that a debtor should not be held liable for costs, losses, and interest due to force majeure or incidental events that prevent the debtor from performing its obligation or doing a prohibited act.⁷¹ In addition, the Indonesian Civil Code also provides that a contract is cancelled if an object agreed in the contract is destroyed, lost, or becomes untradeable.⁷² The object's owner does not need to pay any compensation if the circumstance occurs without fault.⁷³ The provision on force majeure can also be found in other laws, such as banking, construction services, and procurement.⁷⁴ However, the Indonesian Civil Code does not provide a specific definition of what constitutes a force majeure.

A few Indonesian legal experts attempted to define what constitutes a force majeure. Sofwan defines force majeure as a situation where it is impossible to fulfil an obligation or such fulfilment can be done only with extreme measures that result in unreasonable effort or significant financial loss.⁷⁵ Alternatively, Fuady provides a more contemporary definition of force majeure, describing it as a situation where an individual is prevented from fulfilling their contractual obligation due to an unforeseen event when the agreement is made.⁷⁶ The person cannot be held accountable for the event as the person does not act in bad faith.⁷⁷

A comparative look at other countries shows that several civil law jurisdictions offer clearer guidance by providing a definition of force majeure in their civil codes. For example, the Spanish Civil Code provides the definition of force majeure that offers a clearer interpretation and enhances its practical applicability in commercial contexts. It frames force majeure as situations that cannot be foreseen or cannot be avoided, even if they are foreseeable.⁷⁸ This comparative look illustrates how other civil law jurisdictions codify the concept of force majeure, and the lack of an explicit, similar definition under the Indonesian Civil Code.

5. THE APPLICATION OF FORCE MAJEURE DUE TO SHUTTER CONTROL

The satellite data license agreement is substantially equivalent to other commercial contracts. It shares the basic characteristics of commercial contracts and also contains a force majeure clause to protect the licensor from liability for any occurrence beyond its control. The wording of the force majeure clause is constructed very broadly to achieve such objectives.

⁷⁰ For the purpose of this paper, the old Dutch Civil Code (*Burgerlijk Wetboek*) will be referred to as the Indonesian Civil Code.

⁷¹ Indonesian Civil Code (1847), art 1244, 1245.
<https://www.refworld.org/legal/legislation/natlegbod/1847/en/77869>.

⁷² Ibid, art 1444.

⁷³ Ibid, art 1445.

⁷⁴ Rahmat Sadeli Soebagia Soemadipradja. (2010). *Penjelasan Hukum tentang Keadaan Memaksa*. Nasional Legal Reform Program, 73–94.

⁷⁵ Ibid, 34–35.

⁷⁶ Fuady, M. (2001). *Hukum Kontrak (dari Sudut Pandang Hukum Bisnis)*. PT. Citra Aditya Bakti, 113.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Spanish Civil Code, art 1105,
<https://www.mjusticia.gob.es/es/AreaTematica/DocumentacionPublicaciones/Documents/Spanish%20Civil%20Code.pdf#page=214,34>.

- 13.11 **FORCE MAJEURE.** Except for Customer's obligation to make payment under the Customer Agreement or these License Terms, neither party will be liable for any failure or delay in fulfilling or performing any term of these License Terms when and to the extent the failure or delay is caused by or results from acts or events beyond that party's reasonable control, including, without limitation: acts of God; fire; water damage; natural disaster (including earthquakes, storms, and floods); power or utility outages; strikes; war, military action, or act of terrorism; medical crisis, pandemic or epidemic; a total or partial loss, malfunction, or failure of a satellite, ground station, or communications network, whether temporary or permanent; a change in law or regulation (including export control regulations); acts, directives and orders of government and health authorities; or an order or judgment of a court (not arising out of breach by the party of these License Terms). The party suffering a force majeure event will promptly give notice to the other party, stating the period of time the occurrence is expected to continue.

Figure 4. Maxar SecureWatch License.⁷⁹

Force Majeure

Except for your payment obligations, neither party shall be liable for any failure or delay to perform any obligation under these Terms of Use due to fire, explosion, earthquake, storm, flood or other weather, unavailability of necessary utilities or raw materials, Internet service provider failures or delays, denial of service attacks, war, civil unrest, acts of terror, insurrection, riot, disease or viral outbreak or epidemic or pandemic, acts of nature or the public enemy, strikes or other labor problems, any law, act, order, proclamation, decree, regulation, ordinance, or instructions of government or other public authorities, or judgment or decree of a court of competent jurisdiction (not arising out of breach by such party of these Terms of Use), or any other event beyond the reasonable control of the party whose performance is to be excused.

Figure 5. Planet Lab terms of use.⁸⁰

The wording of the force majeure clause above shows that it also aims to protect the licensor from not just unforeseen events but also from acts, regulations, or instructions from government or other public authorities. In other words, the force majeure clause protects the licensor from liability arising from the implementation of the shutter control policy. Therefore, the licensor can invoke the force majeure clause when the shutter control is in effect.

Nonetheless, it bears noting that the enforcement of the contract will also depend on the applicable governing law as agreed by the parties. This is where the contract application becomes intricate as the governing law may not be the law of the country that invokes the shutter control policy, i.e., the US. In section 2 above, the paper elaborates on three types of commercial relationships in Earth observation activities. Recalling the relationship types, the application of the force majeure may not be so complex for a type 1 relationship if the governing law of the contracts is US law. This is because the relationship involves only two parties, each with a direct legal relationship governed by a single satellite data license agreement. As the licensor typically prepares the satellite data license agreement in a standardized form, it will determine the applicable law according to its preference.

The application of the force majeure clause becomes significantly more complex when the contract is governed by non-US law or when a commercial remote sensing structure involves a third party operating under a separate contract, as illustrated in type 2 and type 3 relationships. The Maxar SecureWatch End User License Terms present the first scenario in which the governing law of the contract may vary depending on the customer's domicile. It stipulates that the agreement will be governed by New York and US Federal Law if the customer is domiciled in the US, Canada, or Mexico, and by the laws of England and Wales if the customer is domiciled elsewhere.⁸¹ The second complication arises in a multi-party commercial structure in which the satellite operator, the licensor, and the end-user are connected by distinct contracts. Triggering the force majeure clause due to the implementation of the shutter control

⁷⁹ Maxar. (n.d.). End User License Terms Securewatch® License Version D4-21-21. In Maxar | Legal. Maxar. Retrieved May 23, 2025, from https://maxar-marketing.s3.amazonaws.com/files/legal/FORM_WW0018D_SecureWatchLicense_ver4-21-21.pdf.

⁸⁰ Planet Labs. (2025, December 12). Terms of Use | Planet. Planet.; Planet Labs. https://www.planet.com/terms-of-use/#_7x8ydt96aj79.

⁸¹ Maxar, *supra note* 79, §13.9.

policy may therefore be evaluated differently depending on the governing law of the contract. The legal fragmentation in the multi-party commercial structure consequently raises the potential for dispute when the shutter control policy is enacted.

From a UK legal perspective, the party invoking the force majeure clause must demonstrate that the contract has been frustrated due to the US's implementation of the shutter control policy. This issue does not arise for Tier 1 satellites, as the updated US regulations exempt Tier 1 from shutter control restrictions, as explained in Section 3. However, shutter control remains applicable to remote sensing satellites in Tier 2 and Tier 3 categories. The US government has introduced a three-year time limit for the Tier 3 category. Nonetheless, this limit may be extended upon request by the Secretary of Defense or the Secretary of State and may potentially result in an indefinite extension. In such cases, asserting that the contract is frustrated before a UK court may be more challenging, given the initial three-year cap. A stronger case could be made if the shutter control restrictions had been extended multiple times and had lasted for more than 3 years, rendering performance impossible. Alternatively, the claimant might argue that the contract is frustrated due to an illegal act committed in a friendly foreign country, which is recognized under UK law.⁸²

In comparison, the Indonesian legal perspective may appear less complex than its UK counterpart, as discussed above. Article 1320 of the Indonesian Civil Code strongly upholds the principle of freedom of contract. Subsequently, although the Civil Code does not explicitly define force majeure, Indonesian courts generally apply the criteria agreed upon by the parties in the contract. If the force majeure clause encompasses a broad range of events, similar to the examples mentioned earlier, then the application of the shutter control policy under US law may be applicable under Indonesian law. However, to the author's knowledge, Indonesian courts have not yet addressed a force majeure claim arising from prohibitions by foreign countries, as the UK courts have. A similar approach may be relevant in other civil law jurisdictions. For instance, Article 1091 of the Spanish Civil Code states that a contract serves as law between the parties. Therefore, if a contract includes broad events that qualify as force majeure, such provisions may also trigger force majeure under Spanish law due to the shutter control.

6. CONCLUSION

History shows that the US has supported the commercialization of remote sensing, initially through the Landsat Program, and has been updating its remote sensing regulations in response to technological developments and contemporary commercial needs. The US government recently updated the 15 CFR 960 regulation on the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems in 2020. The update aims to remove certain restrictions to increase the competitiveness of the US remote sensing industry against foreign competitors. The recent update introduced a tier-based licensing structure to achieve the objective. Through this structure, the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation imposes the least stringent licensing requirement on Tier 1 satellites, as they are assessed as low risk from a security perspective. However, satellites in the Tier 2 and Tier 3 categories remain subject to stricter licensing requirements, including shutter control, because they are equipped with technology that may jeopardize the US national security and foreign policy interests.

The US Shutter Control Policy is rooted in PDD-23, with the aim of avoiding any compromise of the US' national security, international obligations, or foreign policy interests. The main concern with this policy is that it creates uncertainty in the implementation of international commercial contracts for remote sensing activities, particularly regarding the collection and distribution of remote sensing data. As elaborated in section 3, the PDD-23 and, subsequently, the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy, empower the executive branch of the US government to limit the collection and distribution of remote

⁸² Peel, *supra* note 59 at 365.

sensing data over an undefined territorial scope for an undefined period of time. Moreover, it does not clarify what constitutes national security and foreign policy interest. Therefore, the broad and vague restriction under PDD-23 and the US Commercial Remote Sensing Policy make the implementation of commercial contracts difficult when the shutter control policy is enacted.

The updated version of the Licensing of Private Land Remote Sensing Space Systems regulation indicates that the US government intends to remove the broad, vague shutter-control restriction to increase the competitiveness of the US remote sensing industry. Nonetheless, such efforts to ease the restriction still have certain shortcomings. The broad and vague restriction remains in place for Tier 2 satellites. For Tier 3 satellites, the regulation introduces a three-year time cap, which may nonetheless be extended upon request by the Secretary of Defense or the Secretary of State, potentially resulting in an indefinite extension. Furthermore, the concepts of national security interest and foreign policy interest remain undefined under the updated version of US 15 C.F.R. 960. These ongoing gaps create significant uncertainty in the implementation of international commercial contracts for remote sensing activities, particularly regarding data-collection and data-distribution obligations.

The doctrine of frustration under UK Common Law sets a high threshold, requiring proof of impossibility or illegality. However, the case of *Taylor v. Caldwell* opens the possibility that a contract can be discharged if performance becomes impossible. However, the tier-based structure introduced by the 2020 regulation complicates this analysis. The initial three-year time cap on shutter control for Tier 3 satellites makes it more difficult to satisfy the impossibility threshold before a UK court, unless the restriction has been extended multiple times beyond the initial period. A stronger argument for frustration could be made if the restrictions persist for well beyond three years. Alternatively, the claimant could present the argument on the basis of the doctrine of discharge by submitting that the shutter control creates a situation where performance of the contract is prohibited by a foreign country and consequently frustrates the contract.

In contrast, Indonesian civil law offers a more flexible approach to force majeure, recognizing a broader range of unforeseen events and emphasizing the principle of freedom of contract. The absence of a statutory definition of force majeure under the Indonesian Civil Code generally leads courts to defer to the parties' contractual terms. If the contract contains a broad force majeure clause, as previously discussed in section 5, the application of the shutter control policy may satisfy the contract's force majeure threshold under Indonesian law. However, Indonesian courts have yet to address a force majeure claim arising specifically from prohibitions by foreign countries, leaving some uncertainty as to how such a claim would ultimately be assessed.

Ultimately, it will all come down to the agreement itself. The analysis in this paper highlights that frustration and force majeure must be assessed on a case-by-case basis, as they depend on the governing provisions specified in the contract. It is therefore recommended that companies engaging in remote sensing activities take proactive steps to ensure legal clarity, including the careful selection of governing law and the precise drafting of force majeure clauses. Moreover, the analysis also presents a strategic insight for Indonesia as it modernizes its space law framework. Ensuring the reliability of Indonesia's jurisdiction is crucial in this context to attract space-related business and investment into the country.